

Synthesis of Phosphorus-containing Heterocycles

M. S. BHATIA*, SUNITA DEVI, RITU JINDAL and BHUPINDER KAUR

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 2 December 1987, accepted 19 February 1988

Synthesis of six-, seven- and nine-membered ring compounds containing phosphorus and oxygen are reported and structures confirmed by pmr and mass spectral studies.

ORGANIC compounds containing phosphorus have gained importance due to their preferential toxicity for cancer cells¹, when released in tissues. Thio-phosphoryl/phosphoryl linkages are common features which are expected to increase the biological activity of organophosphorus compounds as pesticides².

Six-, seven- and nine-membered ring systems containing phosphorus and oxygen atoms have been synthesised by various workers³. In continuation to our earlier work⁴ on the synthesis and biological activity of heterocyclic compounds containing phosphorus and oxygen, a number of heterocyclic compounds containing phosphorus and oxygen have been synthesised and characterised by pmr and mass spectral studies and elemental analysis.

Reaction of 1,4-butanediol with *p,p*-dichlorophenylphosphin oxide in THF in presence of pyridine formed 2-phenyl-1,3,2-dioxaphosphin-2-oxide (1). 2-Phenoxy-1,3,2-dioxaphosphin-2-sulphide (2) was obtained through trans-esterification reaction of 1,4-butanediol and triethylphosphite using catalytic amount of sodium at 160°, followed by treatment of 6 with elemental sulphur in boiling chloroform. Pmr data of 2 and 6 were comparable to that of 1. 4-Methyl-2-phenyl-1,3,2-dioxaphosphin-2-oxide (3) was obtained similarly in 50% yield by treating 1,3-butanediol with *p,p*-dichlorophenylphosphin oxide in pyridine/THF. 2-Phenyl-1,3,2-dioxaphosphin-2-oxide (4) was obtained from 1,4-hexanediol and *p,p*-dichlorophenylphosphin-oxide in THF/pyridine. Attempt to purify this compound by vacuum distillation failed as it decomposed. Therefore, the crude product was purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and chloroform mixture (2 : 1) as eluent.

2-Phenoxy-1,3,2-dioxaphosphin-2-oxide (5) was synthesised by silver oxide oxidation of 2-phenoxy-1,3,2-dioxaphosphin (7; which was obtained by heating 1,6-hexane-diol and triphenyl phosphite).

Experimental

M.ps. and b.ps. are uncorrected Pmr spectra was recorded on a EM/390 spectrometer at 90 MHz and mass spectra (70 eV) on a Jeol-JMS D-300 instrument.

2-Phenyl-1,3,2-dioxaphosphin-2-oxide (1): A mixture of 1,4-butanediol (6.7 g), *p,p*-dichlorophenylphosphin oxide (14.6 g) and pyridine (11.8 g) in dry THF (90 dm³) was refluxed for 12 h on a water-bath. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered

and the solvent evaporated. The resulting product was purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and chloroform mixture (2:1) as eluent to yield 2-phenyl-1,3,2-dioxaphosphepin-2-oxide (12.2 g, 58%) (Found: C, 56.2; H, 6.0, $C_{10}H_{13}O_3P$ calcd. for: C, 56.6; H, 6.2%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 4.1 (m, $2 \times -OCH_2-$), 1.7 (m, $2 \times CH_2$) and 7.5 (m, $5 \times ArH$); m/z 212.

2-Phenoxy-1,3,2-dioxaphosphepin-2-sulphide (2): To a stirred solution of sodium (0.23 g) in dioxane (25 dm³) was added a mixture of triphenylphosphite (31.0 g) and 1,4-butanediol (9.0 g) in dioxane and stirred for 8 h at room temperature and then refluxed in an oil-bath at 160°. The progress of the reaction was checked on tlc. The compound was then purified by distillation under reduced pressure to yield 2-phenoxy-1,3,2-dioxaphosphepin (4; 20 g), b.p. 120°/10 mm (Found: C, 56.3; H, 5.9. $C_{10}H_{13}O_3P$ calcd. for: C, 56.3; H, 5.9%). Compound 4 (5.0 g) and sulphur (1.0 g) in chloroform (10 dm³) were refluxed on a water-bath for 10 h. Evaporation of the solvent yielded 2 (1.75 g) (Found: C, 49.0; H, 5.1. $C_{10}H_{13}O_3PS$ calcd for: C, 49.2; H, 5.3%).

4-Methyl-2-phenyl-1,3,2-dioxaphosphorinone-2-oxide (3): A mixture of 1,3-butanediol (6.79 g), *p,p*-dichlorophenylphosphine-oxide (14.6 g) and pyridine (11.8 g) in dry THF (75 dm³) was refluxed for 12 h at 160°. The reaction mixture was worked up by filtering the residue followed by evaporation of the solvent to yield 3 (59%) (Found: C, 56.2; H, 5.9. $C_{10}H_{13}O_3P$ calcd. for: C, 56.6; H, 6.2%); δ 1.1 (d, CH_3), 2.35 ($CHCH_2$), 1.8 (CH_2CHCH_2), 2.1 ($-OCH_2-$) and 7.3 ($5 \times ArH$); m/z 212.

2-Phenyl-1,3,2-dioxaphosphonin-2-oxide (4): A mixture of 1,6-hexane diol (8.8 g), *p,p*-dichlorophenylphosphine-oxide (14.5 g) and pyridine (11.8 g) was refluxed in dry THF for 18 h. On cooling, solid

pyridine hydrochloride was filtered and the solvent evaporated. The residual viscous oil decomposed in an attempt to purify by vacuum distillation. It was therefore purified by column chromatography over neutral alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and chloroform (3:1) as eluent to give 4 (12.6 g) (Found: C, 55.2; H, 7.5. $C_{12}H_{17}O_3P$ calcd. for: C, 55.6; H, 7.9%); δ 5.0 ($2 \times -OCH_2-$), 1.8 (m, $8 \times CH_2$) and 7.7 ($5 \times ArH$).

2-Phenoxy-1,3,2-dioxaphosphonin-2-oxide (5): A mixture of 1,6-hexanediol (11.8 g) and triphenyl phosphite (31 g) was refluxed for 16 h at 160°. The resulting solid on crystallisation in methanol gave 2-phenoxy-1,3,2-dioxaphosphonin (7; 2.25 g) (Found: C, 55.3; H, 7.0. $C_{12}H_{17}O_3P$ calcd. for: C, 55.6; H, 7.7%). To a stirred solution of silver oxide (1.5 g) in dry benzene (50 dm³) was added 7 (1.0 g) and stirred for 5 h at room temperature. Subsequent evaporation of the solvent yielded 5 (1.1 g) (Found: C, 51.2; N, 7.0. $C_{12}H_{17}O_3P$ calcd. for: C, 51.7; H, 7.3%); δ 4.0 ($2 \times -OCH_2-$), 1.75 (m, $8 \times CH_2$) and 7.5 ($5 \times ArH$); m/z 263.

References

1. L. A. CATES, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1978, 16, 111; H. ARNOLD, BOURSBAZ and N. BROK, *Arsneim.-Forsch.*, 1961, 11, 143.
2. R. W. MARSH, "Systemic Fungicides", Longmans, London, 1972.
3. H. KRCK, W. KUCHEN and H. P. MAHLER, *Org. Mass Spectrom.*, 1980, 15, 581; S. D. POSTER, J. D. SPIVAK, P. L. STEINBULBEL and C. MATZURA, *Phosphorus Sulfur*, 1983, 5, 269.
4. M. S. BHATIA and PAWANJIT, *Experientia*, 1976, 32, 1111; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, 15, 115; *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1975, 1056; M. S. BHATIA, S. P. AHUJA and PAWANJIT, *Ann. Chim.*, 1977, 145; M. S. BHATIA, B. KAUR, S. DEVI and M. C. XAVIERKUTTY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1984, 23, 776.